

DETERMINANTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEMAND FOR ECOLOGICAL PRODUCTS IN THE GROUP OF PEOPLE REPRESENTING GENERATION Z IN THE LIGHT OF RESEARCH

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Abstract

The growing awareness of the need to protect the environment means that more and more consumers want to buy ecological products. The aim of the study, the results of which are discussed in this paper, is to identify selected opportunities and threats for the future, potential increase in demand for pro-ecological offers. The research subjects were students at one of the Polish universities, whose year of birth predisposes them to be included in the so-called Generation Z. The study was conducted using the diagnostic survey method and covered 414 people who completed an online survey questionnaire. The questions constituting the research instrument focused on issues such as: factors taken into account when purchasing goods, types of purchased ecological products, features based on which consumers recognize ecological products, general attitude to ecology, availability of ecological products, density of the network of retail outlets and knowledge of ecological labels. Based on the results obtained, it was found, among other things, that ecology is important to the respondents in their daily lives and that when buying various types of ecological products, they pay attention primarily to the descriptions placed on the packaging, paying less attention to the appearance of the packaging itself. The majority of respondents also believe that ecological products are easily available today. Combined with the positive assessment of the number of retail outlets where respondents can shop, these are conditions that seem to be favorable from the perspective of the future development of markets offering green products. On the other hand, potential barriers to increasing demand can be seen, the most important of which seem to be higher prices and, to a lesser extent, lack of knowledge of eco-labels.

Keywords: Ecological product, demand, factors

1. INTRODUCTION

In an era of growing interest in environmental issues and the concept of sustainable development, more and more people are turning to ecological products. An ecological product is defined in various ways and is often identified with a green or organic product (in the case of food and cosmetics). For example, Gurau & Ranchhod (2025) consider anything that is produced using toxin-free and environmentally friendly ingredients and is certified by a recognized organization to be an ecological product. Similarly, Eerola & Huhtala (2008) emphasize in this context production that has a lower environmental impact, and additionally point out that such products also have different consumer properties compared to conventional products. This last issue is raised in particular in relation to food products. Many studies confirm the positive impact of consuming ecological (organic) food on various health aspects such as obesity or cancer incidence (Glibowski, 2020). Household appliances can also be an ecological product, and energy efficiency is

generally considered to be the basic feature of such devices. The energy efficiency of devices with increasingly lower energy consumption is becoming crucial from the point of view of environmental protection, and devices such as washing machines, refrigerators, freezers, televisions and dishwashers are equipped with special labels indicating energy consumption (Orłowska, 2022).

Taking into account what was said above and the related importance and significance of the demand for ecological products, this paper attempts to answer the following research questions:

- what types of ecological products are of interest to consumers?
- what factors inhibit the growth of consumer demand for ecological products?
- what could cause an increase in demand for these products?

In order to find answers to the above questions, an analysis was conducted using the diagnostic survey method. The group of respondents consisted of people studying at the Faculty of Management at the Lublin University of Technology in Poland. Due to their year of birth, all of these people can be considered to belong to the so-called Generation Z. This generation is currently of interest to both academic and practitioner worlds and is contrasted with other generations such as millennials, generation X and baby boomers in terms of their values, attitudes, behaviours and preferences. (Jayatissa, 2023; Csobanka, 2016).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The topic of demand for ecological products and the accompanying consumer motivations has been present in scientific literature for some time. This has undoubtedly been largely influenced by the growing interest in environmental protection and ecology. On the other hand, authors such as Chowdhury et al. (2021) report on the basis of their analyses that environmental benefits are not the first reason for purchasing ecological products and are replaced by health issues and a specific lifestyle. Health considerations are also mentioned as the most important factor influencing the purchase of ecological products in another work discussing the results of an analysis conducted on a group of consumers in Iran, where, however, the important role of ecological awareness and the level of knowledge represented by consumers and their education is additionally emphasized (Bazhan et al., 2023). The knowledge thread is also present in the article by Brazilian scientists, who clearly state that the local society is less involved in the consumption of ecological products because it does not have sufficient knowledge about these products, and therefore the expansion of this market could occur through appropriate education (Do Prado & Marcondes de Moraes, 2020). The reasons why consumers choose ecological products also include better taste (food) and generally higher quality (Aertsens et al., 2009; Aoki, 2015; Von Meyer-Hoefner et al., 2015).

In addition to the motives for buying ecological products, researchers are also interested in the barriers and limitations that hinder the development of markets for such products. Some of them focus on problems related to knowledge and proper differentiation of ecological labels. This type of limitation is noticed by, among others, Roitner-Schobesberger et al. (2008) who, based on research on the organic vegetable market in Thailand, concluded that potential consumers have problems distinguishing "pesticide safe" labels from organic labels. In another work, it is stated that consumers perceive organically grown agricultural products as products with a questionable appearance that require greater distinction on the market (Radman, 2005). In this context, packaging and information placed on it are of particular importance. According to Soltysiak & Zajac (2022), most consumers of organic food pay attention to the information on the packaging when buying, which means that it is an important factor influencing demand. As Khachataryan et al. (2023) note, packaging is also important for buyers of RTV equipment, as it allows them to obtain information on the energy efficiency and toxicity of materials used by manufacturers. Siuda & Grębosz-Tokarczyk (2025), in turn, claim that their research has shown a positive impact of including pro-ecological elements in product packaging on consumers' purchasing intentions and brand image. Among the destimulants of demand for ecological products, the high price of these items is often mentioned (Bryła, 2016; Brągiel et al., 2015; Matysik-Pejas & Żmuda, 2017). Some authors such as Barge et al. (2015) or Kianpour et al. (2012) however, see a trend of increased acceptance of higher costs of purchasing environmentally friendly products, treating them as a kind of investment that may bring benefits in the future. Another problem in the context of the possibility of increasing interest in ecological products is their availability. It may be difficult in the absence of appropriate promotional activities as well as effective distribution systems (Krishna & Balasubramanian, 2021). The fact that limited availability of ecological products may negatively affect their purchase intentions is also stated in another study summarizing the results of research conducted in India (Nath & Agrawal, 2022). Difficult access may result, among others, from the lack of appropriate retail outlets offering environmentally friendly products. As shown by one of the studies conducted in the first decade of the

twenty-first century, most consumers prefer a supermarket or a specialized organic store as a place to buy ecological products (Naspetti & Zanoli, 2004). Oliveira et al. (2024) also add organic food markets to this, treating them as an interesting alternative to the previously mentioned facilities.

Given the topic of the work, attention should be paid to the issue of Generation Z's attitude towards ecological products. This topic has been relatively rarely analyzed so far. One of the few articles discussing the results of research on this issue is the work by Gomes et al. (2023), in which the authors conclude, among other things, that the willingness of Generation Z people to pay more for green products is dictated by such factors as environmental concerns, a green vision of the future, and green quality. In addition, in the context of the discussed issue, one can cite another study, which is not directly devoted to the issue of demand for ecological products, but the authors consider various aspects of the behavior of the young generation. Some of the aspects discussed may prove to be important from the point of view of potential interest in pro-environmental offers. This concerns the preferred methods of communication and the values they profess. The authors of the work admit that there is no consensus among scientists as to whether Generation Z prefers face-to-face communication or other forms of contact, such as writing, virtual communication and social media. At the same time, they put forward the view that this generation has its own set of altruistic values that reflect their concern for the environment, and is also motivated to make a positive contribution to the world (Jayatissa, 2023).

3. METHODOLOGY

Based on the above literature review and the resulting conclusions regarding the factors influencing the demand for ecological products, a research instrument was created in the form of a survey questionnaire. Next, based on this instrument, a study was conducted using the diagnostic survey method among students of various fields of study at the Faculty of Management of the Lublin University of Technology located in the city of Lublin, in the south-eastern part of Poland. As for the method of obtaining data, the CAWI (Computer-Assisted Web Interview) method was used, i.e. a technique used in quantitative research, in which the questionnaire is completed online. The questionnaire was completed in this way by 414 respondents in January 2025. All respondents were born in the years 1997-2012, and therefore meet the age criterion adopted for classification as Generation Z. The form contained 23 closed questions, of which 8 questions were used for the analysis that is the subject of this paper (Table 1), and each question used a 5-point Likert scale

Table 1. Questions used in the study

No.	Question content
1.	What do you consider when buying a given product? (1- definitely often, 5 – definitely rarely)
2.	What types of ecological products do you buy? (1- definitely often, 5 – definitely rarely)
3.	On what basis, in your opinion, can you say that a given product is ecological? (1 – definitely yes, 5 – definitely no)
4.	What would make you buy more ecological products? (1 – definitely yes, 5 – definitely no)
5.	Do you think that ecological products are easily available? (1 – definitely yes, 5 – definitely no)
6.	Do you think that ecology is important in everyday life? (1 – definitely yes, 5 – definitely no)
7.	Are there many retail outlets in your place of residence? (1 – definitely yes, 5 – definitely no)
8.	Do you know the following symbols placed on product packaging (1 – definitely yes, 5 – definitely no)

Source: Own study.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

The demand for ecological products, similarly to other types of products, is determined by at least several factors that are taken into account by consumers when making a purchase. In one of the questions, respondents were asked to indicate the motives that usually guide them when making purchases. Based on the answers provided, it can be stated that the most important determinants of transactions are the price of a given product and the belief that it will best satisfy the need (Fig. 1). It is worth noting that certificates, quality marks and other similar markings that are placed on packaging are of relatively lesser importance to potential buyers. On the other hand, some importance is attached to the composition of products that are also placed on the outside, and a significant part of them concerns health reasons.

Fig. 1. What do you consider when buying a given product?

Source: Own study

When considering the prospects for the development of markets for individual groups of ecological products, their structural differentiation should be taken into account. For this reason, it was considered important to identify which types of products that can be considered environmentally friendly are purchased more often and which are generally less popular. Figure 2 shows that the differences in consumer preferences in this respect are relatively small. Among other things, attention should be drawn to the slightly higher frequency of buying natural and organic cosmetics than organic food, as well as the fact that some people were unable to clearly determine this frequency. Clearly, ecological cleaning products are purchased the least often.

Fig. 2. What types of ecological products do you buy?

Source: Own study

Another issue raised in the study was the issue of recognizability of ecological products. In order to obtain data on this matter, respondents were asked to indicate which of the listed factors enable them to recognize products with a pro-ecological character. By far the largest number of respondents obtain this knowledge directly from the data placed on the packaging (logo/mark/certificate – definitely yes 28.1% and rather yes 45%, description on the packaging – 16.3% and 49.3% respectively) (Fig. 3). In addition, more than half of the respondents obtain information from websites. However, the relatively smaller role of communication with other people in identifying a given product as ecological is noteworthy.

Fig. 3. In your opinion, on what basis can you state that a given product is ecological?

Source: Own study

As indicated by various studies, one of the reasons why demand for ecological products may be growing is concern for the natural environment and the positive attitude of buyers towards environmental protection.

The vast majority of people surveyed declare that ecology is important to them in their daily lives (Fig. 4). In this group, a larger number of respondents answered “rather yes” (45% of the total sample), while slightly fewer people showed greater determination in this matter (approximately one in four respondents). The opposite position is represented by 10% of those questioned.

Fig. 4. Do you think that ecology is important in everyday life?

Source: Own study

The answers obtained in the survey show that ecological products are perceived as easily accessible by half of the survey participants (Fig. 5). Every tenth respondent is completely certain about this matter, and the number of respondents who are inclined to such a statement constitutes 40% of all those filling out the questionnaire. Although the percentage of people with a different opinion is 16% in total (of which every fourth person asked is completely convinced about it), which can be considered a relatively low indicator, it should be noted that every third person does not have a clearly formed opinion on this subject.

Fig. 5. Do you think that organic products are easily available?

Source: Own study.

The survey form included a question about the retail infrastructure. It included a question about the number of retail outlets, and thus the possibility of making daily purchases. In this case, more than two thirds of respondents stated, by indicating the appropriate options, that there are many retail outlets in their place of residence, while only 15% of respondents gave the opposite answer (Fig. 6.)

Fig. 6. Are there many retail outlets in your place of residence?

Source: Own study

Due to the fact that appropriate labeling of ecological products is indicated by many scientists as one of the conditions for increased interest in this type of offer on the part of consumers, the people participating in the study were asked about their knowledge of ecological symbols. In the questionnaire, under the appropriate point, there was therefore not only the appropriate question, but also a drawing with 12 of the most well-known and most commonly used eco-marks in Poland (Fig. 7). This set included ecological logos placed on various types of products (food, cosmetics, RTV equipment, etc.).

Fig. 7. Ecological labels

Source: Own study based on: <https://www.gov.pl/web/gdos/tajemnicze-ekoznaki>.

The results obtained by means of the survey indicate that a certain number of people are definitely or probably not familiar with such markings (a total of 17% of all respondents), and a further 23% were unable to provide a clear answer as to whether they were familiar with this set or not (Fig. 8). In the latter group of

respondents, some people may have encountered some of the markings, for example, when making purchases, and know what they mean, but selecting the "hard to say" option in this case must certainly be interpreted as a lack of familiarity with at least some of them.

Fig. 8. Do you know the following symbols placed on product packaging?

Source: Own study

The last research thread undertaken in the work is the issue of factors that may influence the increased interest in ecological products and the increase in their purchases. The respondents had several answer options to choose (Fig. 9). They show that what would most encourage consumers to buy larger quantities of ecological products would be their more affordable price (a total of 86.4% of respondents answered "definitely yes" and "rather yes") and improving their own financial situation (69.9% respectively). On the other hand, for the majority of respondents, an intensified advertising campaign and more attractive packaging would be of relatively less importance.

Fig. 9. What would encourage you to buy more ecological products?

Source: Own study

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Based on the results obtained, it can be stated that some of the Generation Z representatives participating in the study often buy various types of ecological products. A larger percentage of respondents declare a positive attitude towards environmental protection and appreciate the importance of ecology in everyday life. Such attitude of Generation Z towards the environment and the need to protect it is written about, among

others, by previously cited authors such as Gomes et al. (2023) and Jayatissa (2023). Considering that this is considered one of the most important determinants of pro-ecological demand, it could be concluded on this basis that interest in such an offer may grow in the near future. However, this does not have to be the case. Contrary to what results from the analyses of Gomes et al. (2023), but also Barge et al. (2015) or Kianpour et al. (2012), the responses of the people included in the study do not indicate in any way a willingness to pay higher prices in the name of contributing to improving the condition of the environment. The respondents seem to attach great importance to the issue of their financial status in the context of purchasing more expensive ecological products. On the one hand, they admit that price is definitely one of the factors they take into account when making a purchase decision, on the other hand, most people believe that a more attractive (and therefore usually lower) price could encourage them to buy ecological products. In addition, there is an improvement in the financial situation, which should also be linked to the problem of prices. All this may lead to the conclusion that higher prices may play a role in the future as a factor inhibiting the growth of markets where ecologically manufactured products are offered. This finding confirms what other researchers found earlier (e.g. Bryła, 2016; Brajgiel et al., 2015; Matysik-Pejas & Żmuda, 2017).

Further conclusions from the study concern the packaging of ecological products and their role in increasing sales. The survey shows that a large group of respondents find ecological products on shelves by reading the information on their packaging. This is consistent not only with their pro-ecological attitude and the desire to buy what was created without harming the environment. It is highly likely that it is also related to caring for one's own health, which according to scholars (including Bazhan et al., 2023; Chowdhury et al., 2021) is at the top of the hierarchy of reasons why pro-ecological products are purchased at all. What results from the respondents' answers also supports the claims present to a greater or lesser extent in works such as Khachataryan et al. (2023) and Sołtysiak & Zajac (2022), where information to read (e.g. regarding energy consumption or materials from which a given product was made) is perceived as key from the point of view of the role of packaging in stimulating demand. However, the appearance of the packaging itself is of relatively lesser importance, which can be seen in the structure of the answers to the question about factors encouraging larger purchases and which seems to be in some opposition to what Radman (2005) and others report. Additionally, in the context of the role of packaging, attention should be paid to the issue of familiarity with eco-labels. The study shows that a certain part of Generation Z may have a problem recognizing them, which is also confirmed by other analyses in which broader social groups were studied (e.g. Roitner-Schobesberger et al., 2008). In this light, the need to educate future, potential consumers about ecological labels, mentioned by some authors, seems justified.

Another area of potential opportunities, but also threats to the expansion of green product markets is their availability. It is influenced, for example, by the number of places where you can shop. The results obtained allow us to conclude that the problem of limited availability should not negatively affect the scale of ecological demand in the future. The vast majority of people taking part in the survey believe that ecological products are easily available today, and in addition, a significant percentage of respondents admit that there are many retail outlets in their place of residence, which should be considered a factor stimulating the growth in demand. However, it should be noted, taking into account the works cited earlier (Naspetti & Zanoli, 2004; Oliveira et al., 2024), that the type of retail outlets where consumers shop is not without significance from the point of view of the breadth of the ecological offer. It seems that there is a need to continue research into the relationship between the size of demand and the places where transactions are made, and additionally also the methods, especially since online purchasing methods have been gaining in importance in recent years, which can open up new, interesting perspectives for both consumers and producers/sellers. In relation to Generation Z, in the case of which there are studies showing that broadly understood virtual contact is of great importance to them (e.g.: Csobanka, 2016; Jayatissa, 2023), searching for opportunities to reach the offer in this way is only becoming more important.

REFERENCE LIST

- Gurau, C., Ranchhod, A. (2005). International green marketing: A comparative study of British and Romanian firms. *International Marketing Review*, 22(5), 547-561. Doi: 10.1108/02651330510624381.
- Eerola, E., & Huhtala, A (2008). Voting for Environmental Policy Under Income and Preference Heterogeneity. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 90(1), 256-266. Doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8276.2007.01042.x.

- Glibowski, P. (2020). Organic food and health. *Roczniki Państwowego Zakładu Higieny*, 71(2), 131-136. Doi: 10.32394/rpzh.2020.0110.
- Orłowska, M. (2022). Saving Energy – a Smart, Ecological and Necessary Trend. *Rocznik Ochrona Środowiska*, 24, 472-480. Doi: 10.54740/ros.2022.033.
- Jayatissa, K.A.D.U. (2023). Generation Z – A new lifeline: A systematic literature review. *Sri Lanka Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3(2), 179-186. Doi: 10.4038/sljssh.v3i2.110.
- Csobanka, Z.E. (2016). The Z Generation. *Acta Technologica Dubnicae*, 6(2), 63-76. Doi: 10.1515/atd-2016-0012.
- Chowdhury, S., Meero, A., Abdu Rahman, A.A., Anwarul Islam, K.M., Zayed, N.M., & Rajibul Hasan, K.B.M. (2021). AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON THE FACTORS AFFECTING ORGANIC FOOD PURCHASING BEHAVIOR IN BANGLADESH: ANALYZING A FEW FACTORS. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 20(4), 1-12. <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/An-empirical-study-on-the-factors-affecting-organic-food-purchasing-behavior-in-bangladesh-analyzing-a-few-factors-1939-6104-20-4-815.pdf> (29.04.2025).
- Bazhan, M., Sabet, F.S., & Borumandnia, N. (2023). Factors affecting purchase intention of organic food products: Evidence from a developing nation context. *Food Science and Nutrition*, 12(5), 3469-3482. Doi: 10.1002/fsn3.4015.
- Do Prado, N.B., & Salati Marcondes de Moraes, G.H. (2020). Environmental awareness, consumption of organic products and gender. *Revista de Gestão*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 27(4), 353-368. Doi: 10.1108/REGE-11-2019-0120.
- Aertsens, J., Verbeke, W., & Mondelaers, K., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2009): Personal determinants of organic food consumption: a review. *British Food Journal*, 111(10), 1140-1167. Doi: 10.1108/00070700910992961.
- Aoki, M. (2015). Consumer loyalty towards locally certified low-input farm products. *British Food Journal*, 117(9), 2300-2312. Doi: 10.1108/bfj-12-2014-0414.
- Von Meyer-Hoefer, M, Nitzko, S., & Spiller, A. (2015). Is there an expectation gap? Consumers' expectations towards organic. *British Food Journal*, 117(5), 1527-1546. Doi: 10.1108/BFJ-07-2014-0252.
- Roitner-Schobesberger, B., Darnhofer, I., Somsook, S., & Vogl, C.R. (2008). Consumer Perceptions of Organic Foods in Bangkok, Thailand. *Food Policy*, 33(2), 112-121. Doi: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2007.09.004.
- Radman, M. (2005). Consumer consumption and perception of organic products in Croatia. *British Food Journal*, 107(4), 263-273. Doi: 10.1108/00070700510589530.
- Siuda, D., & Krawczyk-Grębosz, M. (2025). The Role of Pro-Ecological Packaging in Shaping Purchase Intentions and Brand Image in the Food Sector: An Experimental Study. *Sustainability*, 17, 1744. Doi: 10.3390/su17041744.
- Khachatryan, A., Sakhbivva, A., Kirpicheva, M., Dolgova, M., & Chernov, S. (2023). Consumer Demand for Environmental Friendliness as a New Round of Modern Marketing Development. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 32(5), 4095-4111. Doi: 10.15244/pjoes/166350.
- Bryła, P. (2016). Organic food consumption in Poland: Motives and barriers. *Appetite*, 105, 737-746. Doi: 10.1016/j.appet.2016.07.012.
- Brağiel, E., Pisarek, E.M., & Źródło-Loda, M. (2015). Conditions of Organic Comestible Products Purchase by Cizitens of Krosno. *Economic and Regional Studies*, 8(3), 79-88. <https://www.ers.edu.pl/pdf-93061-27149?filename=UWARUNKOWANIA%20ZAKUPU.pdf> (30.04.2025).
- Matysik-Pejas, R., & Źmuda, J. (2017). Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Process of Organic Food in Krakow Urban Area. *Proceedings of the 2017 International Conference "Economic Science For Rural Development"*, 45, 314-321. https://lufb.llu.lv/conference/economic_science_rural/2017/Latvia_ESRD_45_2017-314-321.pdf (30.04.2025).
- Barge, D.S., More, D.K., & Bholā, S.S. (2015). Eco Friendly Products Attitude towards Pricing. *Pravara Management Review*, 13(2), 29-35. Doi: 10.2139/ssrn.2589415.

- Kianpour, K., Jusoh, A., & Asghari, M. (2012). Importance of Price for Buying Environmentally Friendly Products. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 4(6), 371-375. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/288022609.pdf> (30.04.2025).
- Krishna, R., & Balasubramanian, P. (2021). Understanding the decisional factors affecting consumers' buying behaviour towards organic food products in Kerala. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 234, 00030. Doi: 10.1051/e3sconf/202123400030.
- Nath, V., & Agrawal, R. (2022). Barriers to consumer adoption of sustainable products – an empirical analysis. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 19(3), 858-884. Doi: 10.1108/SRJ-12-2020-0495.
- Sołtysiak, M., & Zajac, D. (2022). Information as a factor in consumer demand for organic food. *Humanities and Social Sciences*, 29(2), 51-64. Doi: 10.7862/rz.2022.hss.12.
- Naspetti, S., & Zanolli, R. (2004). Do consumers care about where they buy organic products? A means-end study with evidence from Italian data. In: Baourakis, G. *Marketing Trends for Organic Food in the 21st Century*, 239-255. Doi: 10.1142/9789812796622_0015.
- De Souza Couto Oliveira, J., Perim de Faria, C., Freitas, J. (2024). Organic food consumers and producers: Understanding their profiles, perceptions, and practices. *Heliyon*, 10, e31385. Doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e31385.
- Gomes, S., Lopes, J.M., & Nogueira, S. (2023). Willingness to pay more for green products: A critical challenge for Gen Z. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 390, 136092. Doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136092.
- Jayatissa, K.A.D.U. (2023). Generation Z – A New Lifeline: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sri Lanka Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3(2), 179-186. Doi: 10.4038/sljssh.v3i2.110.